

COMPREHENSIVE ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION FOR STABILITY STUDY AND IMPURITY ANALYSIS OF ANTIVIRAL DRUGS USING RP-HPLC

Swati Gondaliya¹, Janki Patel^{*2}, Ragin Shah³, Divyakant Patel⁴, Hiren Doshi⁵

¹Research Scholar, Swarnim Startup and Innovation university.

^{*2}Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Quality Assurance, Sharda School of Pharmacy, Pethapur, Gandhinagar.

^{*3}Professor and principal Department of Quality Assurance, Arihant School of pharmacy, Adalaj, Gandhinagar.

⁴Principal, Sharda School of Pharmacy, Pethapur, Gandhinagar.

⁵Professor, Dept. of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Pro vice chancellor, Swarnim Startup and Innovation University, Gandhinagar.

Article Received on
12 August 2025,

Revised on 01 Sept. 2025,
Accepted on 21 Sept. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17224503>

***Corresponding Author**

Janki Patel

Associate Professor,
Department of
Pharmaceutical Quality
Assurance, Sharda School of
Pharmacy, Pethapur,
Gandhinagar.

ABSTRACT

A robust and validated stability-indicating RP-HPLC method was developed for the simultaneous estimation of Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate in Dolutegravir, Lamivudine, and Tenofovir (DLT) combination tablets. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Kinetex Biphenyl column (100 × 4.6 mm, 2.6 μm) using a gradient elution with buffer and an organic phase consisting of acetonitrile, methanol, and isopropyl alcohol. Detection was performed at 260 nm with a total run time of 97 minutes. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines and demonstrated specificity, linearity (correlation coefficient $R^2 = 1.000$ for both analytes), precision, accuracy, robustness, and adequate limits of detection and quantification. Forced degradation studies under acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, humidity, and photolytic conditions confirmed that the method can reliably separate analytes from their degradation products, with no interference from excipients. The developed method

proved to be selective, precise, and robust, making it suitable for routine quality control and stability testing of DLT tablets.

KEYWORDS: Lamivudine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate, DLT Tablets, Stability-Indicating Method, RP-HPLC, Method Validation.

INTRODUCTION

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) is a virus that causes the syndrome of acquired immune deficiency (AIDS) and is transmitted by contact with blood and body fluids that are infected. HIV infects the body's immune cells, which are important for battling infections, called CD4 positive (CD4+) T cells. HIV turns these cells into factories that create more HIV viruses to infect other healthy cells, thereby killing the CD4+ cells. These three drugs are used as antiretroviral medicines which are used for HIV or AIDS prevention and treatment. Three key antiretroviral agents - Lamivudine, Tenofovir and Dolutegravir - have emerged as a potent fixed-dose combination for managing HIV infection. Lamivudine, chemically known as 4-amino-1-[(2R,5S)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl] pyrimidin-2(1H)-one, is a nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor (NRTI) that interferes with HIV viral RNA-dependent DNA polymerase. It demonstrates activity against both HIV-1 and HIV-2, while also showing efficacy in chronic hepatitis B treatment. The drug acts by terminating the nascent viral DNA chain through incorporation into viral DNA. Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate, a prodrug of tenofovir, is chemically designated as (([(2R)-1-(6-amino-9H-purin-9-yl) propan-2-yl] oxy) methyl) phosphonic acid. Upon oral administration, it undergoes conversion to tenofovir, an acyclic nucleoside phosphonate an analogue of adenosine monophosphate. The active metabolite competitively inhibits HIV reverse transcriptase, leading to DNA chain termination. Dolutegravir, with the chemical name (4R,12aS)-N-[(2,4-difluorophenyl) methyl]-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6,8-dioxo-3,4,6,8,12,12a-hexahydro-2H-pirido [1',2':4,5] pyrazino[2,1-b] [1,3] oxazine-9-carboxamide, belongs to the integrase strand transfer inhibitor class. It prevents viral DNA integration into host cell DNA by binding to the integrase active site and blocking the strand transfer step of retroviral DNA integration.^[1,9]

Fig:1 Chemical Structure of Lamivudine^[10] Fig:2 Chemical Structure of Dolutegravir^[11]

Fig:3 Chemical Structure of Tenofovir.^[12]

A stability indicating method accurately measures the changes in active ingredients concentration without interference from other degradation products, impurities and excipients. It is classified into two types, Specific Stability Indicating Method and Selective Stability Indicating Method. Related substance are the impurities in pharmaceuticals which are unwanted chemicals that remain with the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API), or development during stability testing. Related components are impurities which are derived from the drug substance and therefore not including impurities from excipient. Related Substance include degradation products, Synthetic impurities of drug substance and manufacturing process impurities from the drug product.^[14,15]

METHOD AND MATERIAL

Chemical and reagents: Sodium lauryl sulphate (AR grade (Make: SDFCL or equivalent), Ammonium acetate (AR grade), Ammonia solution (AR grade), Isopropyl alcohol (HPLC grade), Acetonitrile (HPLC grade), Glacial acetic acid (AR grade), Methanol (HPLC grade (Make: Rankem or equivalent), Water (Milli-Q or equivalent).

Chromatographic Condition: Chromatographic separation was performed on a Kinetex Biphenyl column (100 Å, 100 × 4.6 mm, 2.6 µm particle size). The mobile phase was delivered at a flow rate of 0.6 mL/min, with the column oven maintained at 30 °C to ensure consistent temperature control. The sample cooler was set at 20 °C, and an injection volume of 15 µL was used for each analysis. Detection was carried out using a UV detector at a wavelength of 260 nm. The total run time for each injection was 97 minutes. The rinsing solvent employed was a mixture of water and methanol in a 100:900 (v/v) ratio to minimize carryover and maintain system cleanliness.

Gradient program

Time (Minutes)	Mobile phase- A (%)	Mobile phase- B (%)
0	100	0
8	100	0
30	85	15
70	50	50
80	25	75
81	100	0
97	100	0

Preparation of diluted glacial acetic acid: Transfer 10 mL of glacial acetic acid into a 100 mL volumetric flask containing about 70 mL of water. Dilute to volume with water and mix well.

Preparation of buffer solution: Accurately weigh and transfer about 0.77 g of ammonium acetate in 1000 mL of water, mix well and sonicate to dissolve. Adjust the pH of solution to 6.8 ± 0.05 by using diluted (1:100) ammonia solution or diluted glacial acetic acid. Mix well and sonicate to degas. Do not filter.

Preparation of mobile phase A: Prepare a mixture of buffer solution and acetonitrile in the ratio of 1000: 5% v/v. Sonicate to degas prior to use.

Preparation of mobile phase B: Prepare a mixture of acetonitrile: methanol: isopropyl alcohol in the ratio of 700:200:100% v/v/v. Sonicate to degas prior to use.

Note: The mobile phase is stable up to 4 days at Room temperature.

Preparation of diluent: Weigh and transfer about 20 g of sodium lauryl sulfate and 1.54 g of ammonium acetate into a 1000 mL clean and dry volumetric flask or glass beaker. Add about 700 mL of water and sonicate to dissolve. Allow the solution to attain room temperature. Dilute to volume with water and mix well.

Preparation of blank solution: Use diluent as a blank solution.

Preparation of standard stock solution: Accurately weigh and transfer about 32 mg of Lamivudine working/reference standard and 32 mg of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate working/reference standard into a 100 mL clean and dry volumetric flask. Add about 70 mL of methanol and sonicate to dissolve. Allow the solution to attain room temperature. Dilute to volume with methanol and mix well.

Preparation of standard solution: Transfer 3 mL of standard stock solution into a 200 mL clean and dry volumetric flask, dilute to volume with diluent and mix well.

Preparation of Mono POC Dimer impurity stock solution for peak identification: Accurately weigh and transfer about 3.6 mg of Mono POC Dimer impurity into a 20 mL clean and dry volumetric flask. Add about 15 mL of methanol and sonicate to dissolve. Allow the solution to attain room temperature. Dilute to volume with methanol and mix well.

Preparation of Mono POC Dimer impurity solution for peak identification: Transfer 1 mL of Mono POC Dimer impurity stock solution for peak identification into a 50 mL clean and dry volumetric flask, dilute to volume with diluent and mix well.

Preparation of sample solution: Accurately weigh 20 intact tablets and determine the average weight of tablets. Accurately weigh 5 intact tablets and crush into a fine powder with mortar pestle and mix well. Accurately weigh and transfer the tablet powder equivalent to 150 mg of Lamivudine into a 25 mL clean and dry volumetric flask. Add 2.5 mL of water and shake well. Add about 15 mL of methanol and sonicate for 30 minutes with intermittent shaking at temperature below 25°C. Allow the solution to attain room temperature. Dilute to volume with methanol and mix well. Centrifuge the resulting solution at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Transfer 4 mL of the supernatant solution into a 50 mL clean and dry volumetric flask. Dilute to volume with diluent and mix well. Filter the solution through Nylon 0.2 μ (Millipore Millex-GN) filter by discarding first 5 mL of filtrate.

Preparation of excipient blend solution containing Dolutegravir

Accurately weigh and transfer excipient blend containing Dolutegravir equivalent to 150 mg of Lamivudine into a 25 mL clean and dry volumetric flask. Add 2.5 mL of water and shake well. Add about 15 mL of methanol and sonicate for 30 minutes with intermittent shaking at temperature below 25°C. Allow the solution to attain room temperature. Dilute to volume with methanol and mix well. Centrifuge the resulting solution at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes. Transfer 4 mL of the supernatant solution into a 50 mL clean and dry volumetric flask. Dilute to volume with diluent and mix well. Filter the solution through Nylon 0.2 μ (Millipore Millex-GN) filter by discarding first 5 mL of filtrate.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Method Development and Validation

Separately inject the equal volumes of blank solution, excipient blend (placebo) solution, standard solution, sample solution and record the chromatograms.

Injection scheme: Different solution was injected including Blank solution (3 injection), Excipient blend solution (1 injection), Standard solution (6 injection), Mono POC Dimer impurity solution for peak identification (1 injection), Sample solution (1 injection), Blank solution (1 injection), Bracketing standard (standard solution) after completion of sequence &/or after injecting 6 injections of sample solution whichever is earlier (1 injection).

Retention Time was found 18.37 min for Lamivudine, 27.21 min for Mono-POC PMPA, 20.89 min for Impurity J, 34.97 min for Lamivudine Dimer, 37.65 min for Mono POC Dimer and 54.53 min for Tenofovir Disoproxil.

Validation

Specificity (Forced Degradation Study)

Prepared blank solution and Standard solution as per analytical method. Degrading agents will be added separately to Lamivudine USP API, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate API, Excipient blend (containing Dolutegravir sodium), Dolutegravir 50 mg, Lamivudine 300 mg and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate 300mg Tablets. Degrading agents will be HCl (Acid degradation), NaOH (Base degradation), 5% Hydrogen peroxide (Oxidative degradation), Heat Degradation-Solid state(50°C), Heat Degradation-Solution state (60°C), Humidity degradation (40°C/75% RH) and Photolytic degradation.

Fig: 4 Forced degradation – Blank solution.

Fig: 5 Forced degradation – Excipient blend solution.

Fig: 6 Forced degradation – Standard solution.

Fig: 7 Forced degradation –Sample Solution-Untreated.

Fig: 8 Forced degradation –Sample Solution-Acid Degradation.

Fig: 9 Forced degradation –Sample Solution-Base Degradation.

Fig: 11 Forced degradation –Sample Solution- Heat degradation (Solid state).

Fig:10 Forced degradation –Sample Solution- Heat degradation (Solution state).

Fig:12 Forced degradation –Sample Solution- Humidity Degradation.

Fig:13 Forced degradation –Sample Solution- Photolytic Degradation.

Fig: 14 Forced degradation –Sample Solution- Peroxide Degradation.

Table 1: Mass balance during forced degradation between Assay and Related substances method for Lamivudine.

Sr. No.	Stress type	Degrading agents / Conditions/Exposure period	% Assay of Lamivudine (Assay)	%Total impurities (Lamivudine)	Mass balance
1	Untreated Tablets	NA	95.6	0.0000	NA
2	Acid degradation	For 60 minutes at RT	99.2	0.0000	103.78
3	Base degradation	For 60 minutes at RT	99.5	0.0000	104.09
4	Peroxide degradation	For 60 minutes at 60°C in water bath	96.2	0.0000	100.65
5	Heat degradation (Solid state)	For 7 Hours	95.2	0.0000	99.64
6	Heat degradation (Solution state)	For 1 hour in water bath	97.5	0.0000	102.06
7	Humidity degradation	For 24 hours	95.1	0.0000	99.53
8	Photolytic degradation	1.2 million lux hours and 200-watt hrs. / m ²	95.3	0.0983	99.81

Table 2: Mass balance during forced degradation between Assay and Related substances method for Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate.

Sr. No.	Stress type	Degrading agents / Conditions/ Exposure period	% Assay of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate (Assay)	%Total impurities	Mass balance
1	Untreated Tablets	NA	98.6	1.1251	NA
2	Acid degradation	For 60 minutes at RT	85.8	13.2695	99.43
3	Base degradation	For 60 minutes at RT	81.6	16.5409	98.41
4	Peroxide degradation	For 60 minutes at 60°C in water bath	98.6	1.8263	100.77
5	Heat degradation (Solid state)	For 7 Hours	97.6	1.0711	98.94
6	Heat degradation (Solution state)	For 1 hour in water bath	99.1	1.4611	100.86
7	Humidity degradation	For 24 hours	96.5	1.3297	98.10
8	Photolytic degradation	1.2 million lux hours and 200-watt hrs. / m ²	97.3	1.0629	98.69

Observation and conclusion: No degradant peaks due to excipient blend are observed at the retention time of Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate peaks in all conditions of degradation. The degradant peaks are well separated from Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate peaks. The peak purity criteria for Lamivudine peak passes in all conditions of degradation, when Lamivudine USP API is subjected to different stress conditions. The peak purity criteria for Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate peak passes in all conditions of degradation, when Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate API is subjected to different stress conditions. The peak purity criteria for Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate peaks passes in all conditions of degradation, when Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate 300 mg, Dolutegravir 50 mg and Lamivudine 300 mg Tablets was subjected to different stress conditions. Based on above observation, it is concluded that the analytical method is specific

LOD and LOQ

Limit of detection: Prepared blank solution, standard solution and Mono POC Dimer impurity solution for peak identification as per analytical method. Prepared LOD level concentration of Lamivudine, Tenofovir Disoproxil, Mono POC PMPA, Imp. J, Mono POC Dimer and Lamivudine Dimer and inject.

Table 3: Results of LOD Verification (S/N ratio).

Name	Lamivudine	Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	Mono POC PMPA	Mono POC Dimer	Impurity J	Lamivudine dimer
1	389	255	410	240	145	130
2	331	227	349	204	134	121
3	299	198	314	184	162	147

Conclusion: Signal to noise ratio of LOD solution is more than 3. Hence, it is concluded that the LOD is verified.

Limit Of quantification: Prepared blank solution, standard solution and Mono POC Dimer impurity solution for peak identification as per analytical method. Prepared LOQ concentration of Lamivudine, Tenofovir Disoproxil, Mono POC PMPA Impurity, Impurity J, Mono POC Dimer and Lamivudine Dimer. Injected six replicates into HPLC. Calculated the % RSD of peak areas and signal to noise ratio.

Table 4: Results of LOQ – Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate.

Sr. No.	Peak area of Lamivudine	S/N ratio	Peak area of Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate	S/N ratio
1	11438	1537	7864	896
2	11387	1070	8271	641
3	11363	918	7923	536
4	11356	800	7860	466
5	11361	719	7735	413
6	11380	1072	7829	627
Mean	11381		7914	
Standard Deviation	30.610		185.402	
(%) RSD	0.3		2.3	

Conclusion: % RSD of peak areas of six injections at LOQ concentration meets the pre-established acceptance criteria. Also, S/N ratio of LOQ precision test is more than 10. Hence, it is concluded that the established LOQ is precise.

Linearity

Prepared a series of linearity standard solutions (Six levels) of Lamivudine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate and their impurities over a range starting from LOQ to 150% of specified limit concentration of known impurities, Lamivudine w.r.t. Impurity J for stability and Tenofovir Disoproxil w.r.t. Mono- POC PMPA Impurity for stability.

Fig: 15 Graph of Linearity for Lamivudine for LOQ to 150% Level (Lamivudine).

Conclusion: A linearity graph of the average peak area of Lamivudine against the concentration in ppm is plotted and is found as a straight-line graph. The correlation coefficient is 1.000. The method is found linear in the range of LOQ to 150% level of system suitability solution concentration of Lamivudine.

Fig: 16 Graph of Linearity for Tenofvir Disoproxil Fumarate from LOQ to 150% level.

Conclusion

A linearity graph of the average peak area of Tenofvir Disoproxil Fumarate against the concentration in ppm is plotted and is found as a straight line graph. The correlation coefficient is 1.000. The method is found linear in the range of LOQ to 150% level of system suitability solution concentration of Tenofvir Disoproxil Fumarate.

Precision

Prepared blank solution, standard solution and Mono POC Dimer impurity solution for peak identification as per analytical method and inject into HPLC.

Table 5: System suitability results- System precision.

Sr.No.	Lamivudine	Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate
1	255236	153901
2	255754	155021
3	254827	152544
4	255070	151827
5	255074	153492
6	255315	154824
Mean	255213	153602
Standard Deviation	313.842	1255.509
(%) RSD	0.1	0.8
Tailing factor	1.10	0.99
Theoretical plates	90410	563706

Conclusion

% RSD for peak area of six replicate injections is within the pre-established acceptance criteria and system suitability results meet as per analytical method. Hence, it is concluded that the system is precise.

Method Precision Prepared six spiked sample with known impurities at limit level for Dolutegravir 50 mg, Lamivudine 300 mg and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate 300 mg Tablets and Injected HPLC system.

Table 6: Results of Method Precision (in %).

Sample No	Mono POC PMPA	Mono POC Dimer	Impurity J	Lamivudine Dimer	Any unspecified impurity
Sample	0.8368	0.7005	1.1793	0.1839	0.1170
Sample	0.8221	0.7146	1.2009	0.1873	0.1166
Sample	0.7960	0.7092	1.1912	0.1860	0.1246
Sample	0.8165	0.7147	1.2027	0.1878	0.1172
Sample	0.8164	0.7135	1.1994	0.1878	0.1197
Sample	0.8061	0.7091	1.1937	0.1860	0.1173
Mean	0.8156	0.7102	1.1945	0.1864	0.1187
Standard	0.0139	0.0054	0.0086	0.0015	0.0030
(%) RSD	1.7	0.8	0.7	0.8	2.5

Conclusion

The analytical method meets the pre-established acceptance criteria for method precision.

Hence it is concluded that the method is precise.

Intermediate precision

Prepared six spiked sample with known impurities at limit level for Dolutegravir 50 mg, Lamivudine 300 mg and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate 300 mg Tablets and Injected HPLC system on a different day using column of same make with different sr. no /lot no. and inject into a different HPLC system using the method as described under method of analysis.

Table 7: Results of Intermediate precision (in %).

Sample No	Mono POC PMPA	Mono POC Dimer	Impurity J	Lamivudine Dimer	Any unspecified impurity
Sample	0.8662	0.7879	1.2809	0.1900	0.1355
Sample	0.8187	0.7880	1.2823	0.1898	0.1229
Sample	0.8455	0.7919	1.2892	0.1917	0.1253
Sample	0.8449	0.7925	1.2905	0.1924	0.1234
Sample	0.8301	0.7945	1.2935	0.1924	0.1252
Sample	0.8256	0.7884	1.2823	0.1906	0.1267
Mean	0.8385	0.7905	1.2864	0.1911	0.1265
Standard	0.0172	0.0028	0.0052	0.0011	0.0046
(%) RSD	2.1	0.4	0.4	0.6	3.6

Conclusion

The analysis of the same batch of the drug product was carried out on six sample solutions by using column of the same make having different sr. no. on different day within the same laboratory using different HPLC system. The % RSD results of % any unspecified impurity and total impurities of six sample solutions is within the pre-established acceptance criteria as per protocol.

Filter validation- Prepare spiked sample at limit level and filter the solution with, 0.45 μ m filter and compare the result with unfiltered solution.

Table 8: Results (in %) - Filter validation.

Sample No	Mono POC PMPA	Mono POC Dimer	Impurity J	Lamivudine Dimer	Any unspecified impurity
Unfiltered	0.8505	0.9010	1.2793	0.1891	0.1253
Filtered	0.8662	0.7879	1.2809	0.1900	0.1355
Filtered	0.8187	0.7880	1.2823	0.1898	0.1229
Filtered	0.8455	0.7919	1.2892	0.1917	0.1253
Filtered	0.8449	0.7925	1.2905	0.1924	0.1234
Filtered	0.8301	0.7945	1.2935	0.1924	0.1252
Mean	0.8426	0.8093	1.2859	0.1909	0.1262

Standard	0.0164	0.0449	0.0058	0.0014	0.0046
%RSD	2.0	5.6	0.5	0.7	3.7

Conclusion: The analytical method meets the pre-established acceptance criteria for filter validation study as per protocol. Hence, 0.45 μm Nylon filter.

Recovery

Prepared sample as such, spiked impurities Imp. J, Mono POC Dimer, Lamivudine dimer, Mono POC PMPA at LOQ level, 50%, 100%, 150% in sample solution of Dolutegravir 50 mg, Lamivudine 300 mg and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate Tablets.

Table: 9 Results - Accuracy (% Recovery)– Impurity J.

Level of Addition	Theoretical Limit level (%)	Amount found in %	Amount of added in %	Recovery (%)	Mean (%) recovery	RSD (%)
First Level (LOQ)	0.05	0.0521	0.0511	101.9569	101.8	0.2
		0.0519	0.0511	101.5655		
		0.0521	0.0511	101.9569		
Second Level (Rec-50%)	0.60	0.6143	0.6157	99.7726	99.5	0.2
		0.6166	0.6199	99.4676		
		0.6076	0.6113	99.3947		
Third Level (Rec-100%)	1.20	1.2270	1.2198	100.5902	100.7	0.1
		1.2346	1.2248	100.8001		
		1.2171	1.2068	100.8534		
Fourth Level (Rec-150%)	1.80	1.8628	1.8580	100.2583	100.4	0.1
		1.8679	1.8603	100.4085		
		1.8282	1.8210	100.3953		

Conclusion

The analytical method meets the pre-established acceptance criteria for recovery. All impurities recovery found more than 90% in each level. Hence, it is concluded that the method is accurate.

Robustness

Prepared sample solution and sample spiked with known impurities solution and injected with change condition as per below, change in flow rate (± 0.1 mL/minutes), Change in wavelength (± 2 nm), Change in column oven temperature ($\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$).

Conclusion

The analysis of Dolutegravir 50 mg, Lamivudine 300 mg and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate 300 mg Tablets was carried out with change in column (same make different sr. no.), flow

rate, wavelength and column oven temperature. The system suitability results were found to meet the pre-established criteria as per analytical method at all the conditions. % RSD between results obtained with changed condition and result of method precision is as per acceptance criteria given in method precision. There is change in retention time of Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate observed in robustness study. From the above data it is concluded that, the method is robust for said parameters.

OVERALL CONCLUSION

The above summary and the validation data summarized in this document shows that the analytical method for Related substances of Lamivudine and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate in Dolutegravir 50 mg, Lamivudine 300 mg and Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate 300 mg Tablets by HPLC is selective, specific, precise, linear, accurate and robust for change in column (same make but different sr.no.), change in flow rate, wavelength and column oven temperature. The mobile phase is stable up to 4 days at room temperature. The standard solution is stable up to 5 days at room temperature and sample solution is stable up to 6 hours at room temperature. Hence, the analytical method is validated and can be used for routine analysis.

REFERENCE

1. Haribabu, Y., et al. "Method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of lamivudine, dolutegravir and tenofovir disoproxil fumarate in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form using RP-HPLC and its application to in-vitro dissolution study." *J. Med. P'ceutical allied Sci.*, 10 2021.
2. SK Mastanamma, J Asha Jothi, P. Saidulu, M Varalakshmi, 2018. Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of lamivudine, tenofovir alafenamide and dolutegravir bulk and their combined dosage form, *pharm methods* 9, 49-55.
3. Ippe, Durga Bhavani, and Nagaraju Pappula. "Development and Validation of a Gradient RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Lamivudine, Tenofovir Disoproxil Fumarate, and Dolutegravir in Combined Pharmaceutical Formulation." *Journal of Pharma Insights and Research*, 2025; 3(1): 252-260.
4. Basu S, Swain PK, Singh P, Mahalik K. Development and validation of stability-indicating HPLC method for determination of dolutegravir sodium. *Int J ChemTech Res.*, 2018; 11(8): 334-43.

5. Patel SB, Patel BG, Patel DK, Patel M. Development and validation of HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of tenofovir disoproxil fumarate and lamivudine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. *Int J Pharm Sci Res.*, 2019; 10(4): 1871-7.
6. Kandimalla A, Srinivas N, Ravindra N, Venkateshwarlu G. Development and validation of stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination of dolutegravir and lamivudine. *J Chromatogr Sci.*, 2020; 58(6): 547-55.
7. Wang X, Cattaneo D, Baldelli S, Pasipanodya J, Gianelli E, Gervasoni C. The validation of analytical methods for drug quantification in blood plasma or serum. *Bioanalysis.*, 2018; 10(7): 517-31.
8. Kavitha KY, Geetha G, Hariprasad R, Kaviarasu M, Venkatnarayanan R. Development and validation of stability indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of lamivudine, tenofovir disoproxil fumarate and dolutegravir bulk and their combined dosage form. *Int J Pharm Sci Drug Res.*, 2019; 11(2): 43-52.
9. Belouafa S, Habti F, Benhar S, Belafkih B, Tayane S, Hamdouch S, et al. Statistical tools and approaches to validate analytical methods. *J Anal Sci Technol*, 2017; 8(1): 1-12.
10. Prava, Rajkumar, et al. "RP-HPLC method development and validation for the simultaneous determination of lamivudine, abacavir and dolutegravir in pharmaceutical dosage forms." *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2017; 168-181.
11. Noorbasha, Khaleel, and Sharmila Nurbasha. "A new validated stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for simultaneous quantification of dolutegravir and lamivudine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form." *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2020; 6(1): 39.
12. Zhang, Zhenzhen, et al. "Development of a validated HPLC method for the determination of tenofovir disoproxil fumarate using a green enrichment process." *Analytical Methods* 2015; 7(15): 6290-6298.
13. Rathod, Nikita, and P. A. I. Prajapati. "Analytical Method Development and Validation of Stability Indicating Method and Related Substance by Using RP-HPLC of Drug Substance." *Pharma Science Monitor*, 2017; 8(2): 409-419.
14. ICH Q3A (R2) Impurities in new drug substance: Text and Methodology, International conference of harmonization, (2006) IFPMA, Geneva, Switzerland.
15. International conference on harmonisation of technical requirements for registration of pharmaceuticals for human use, Stability testing of new drug substances and products Q1A(R2) 6 February 2003.